

(51) International Patent Classification:

H01Q 1/28 (2006.01) *B64C 39/00* (2006.01)
H01Q 1/46 (2006.01)

(21) International Application Number:

PCT/IB2017/057346

(22) International Filing Date:

22 November 2017 (22.11.2017)

(25) Filing Language:

English

(26) Publication Language:

English

(30) Priority Data:

17/70043 12 January 2017 (12.01.2017) FR

(71) Applicant: **TEKCEM** [FR/FR]; 12 chemin des Hauts de Clairefontaine, 78580 Maule (FR).

(72) Inventors: **BROYDE, Frederic**; 12 chemin des Hauts de Clairefontaine, 78580 Maule (FR). **CLAVELIER, Evelyne**; 12 chemin des Hauts de Clairefontaine, 78580 Maule (FR).

(81) Designated States (*unless otherwise indicated, for every kind of national protection available*): AE, AG, AL, AM, AO, AT, AU, AZ, BA, BB, BG, BH, BN, BR, BW, BY, BZ, CA, CH, CL, CN, CO, CR, CU, CZ, DE, DJ, DK, DM, DO, DZ, EC, EE, EG, ES, FI, GB, GD, GE, GH, GM, GT, HN, HR, HU, ID, IL, IN, IR, IS, JO, JP, KE, KG, KH, KN, KP,

KR, KW, KZ, LA, LC, LK, LR, LS, LU, LY, MA, MD, ME, MG, MK, MN, MW, MX, MY, MZ, NA, NG, NI, NO, NZ, OM, PA, PE, PG, PH, PL, PT, QA, RO, RS, RU, RW, SA, SC, SD, SE, SG, SK, SL, SM, ST, SV, SY, TH, TJ, TM, TN, TR, TT, TZ, UA, UG, US, UZ, VC, VN, ZA, ZM, ZW.

(84) Designated States (*unless otherwise indicated, for every kind of regional protection available*): ARIPO (BW, GH, GM, KE, LR, LS, MW, MZ, NA, RW, SD, SL, ST, SZ, TZ, UG, ZM, ZW), Eurasian (AM, AZ, BY, KG, KZ, RU, TJ, TM), European (AL, AT, BE, BG, CH, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, ES, FI, FR, GB, GR, HR, HU, IE, IS, IT, LT, LU, LV, MC, MK, MT, NL, NO, PL, PT, RO, RS, SE, SI, SK, SM, TR), OAPI (BF, BJ, CF, CG, CI, CM, GA, GN, GQ, GW, KM, ML, MR, NE, SN, TD, TG).

Published:

— with international search report (Art. 21(3))

(54) Title: ANTENNA COMPRISING AN UNMANNED AIRCRAFT

FIG. 1

(57) Abstract: The invention relates to an antenna for radiocommunication, for instance an antenna for radio reception and/or radio emission in the frequency range 1.8 MHz to 30 MHz. An antenna for radiocommunication in a given frequency band comprises: an unmanned aircraft (1) comprising 2 "aircraft power input terminals" to receive electric power; a cable (2) comprising 2 electrical conductors which are insulated from one another, the first end of each of the electrical conductors being coupled to one of the aircraft power input terminals; a coupling network (3) comprising 2 "coupling network power input terminals" to receive electric power outside the given frequency band, the coupling network comprising 2 paths for a direct current, the coupling network comprising a "signal terminal" used for signals in the given frequency band, the coupling network comprising 2 paths for a current in the given frequency band.

Antenna comprising an unmanned aircraft

FIELD OF THE INVENTION

The invention relates to an antenna for radiocommunication, for instance an antenna for
5 radio reception and/or radio emission in the frequency range 1.8 MHz to 30 MHz.

The French patent application No. FR1770043 of 12 January 2017, entitled “Antenne
comportant un aéronef sans pilote” is incorporated by reference.

PRIOR ART

Efficient antennas for operation below 30 MHz must reach a sufficient height above ground,
10 and possibly above surrounding trees or buildings. A tubular pole or mast (with or without guys)
may be satisfactory in the 10 MHz to 30 MHz frequency range. Below 10 MHz, there is
typically a need to use a lattice tower. To avoid the cost, the time and the space needed to erect
a mast or a tower, it is sometime possible to use a kite or a Charlière (gas balloon) to support an
approximately vertical antenna. These approaches have the following drawbacks: flying a kite
15 is impractical and not always possible, in particular if the wind is not sufficient; the position of
a Charlière is difficult to control in the presence of wind; using an hydrogen-filled balloon is
dangerous and expensive ; and using an helium-filled balloon is very expensive.

Consequently, there is no inexpensive solution to the problem of realizing a reliable and
efficient antenna for operation below 30 MHz, without the time and the space needed to erect
20 a mast or a tower.

SUMMARY OF THE INVENTION

The purpose of the invention is an antenna, without the above-mentioned limitations of
known techniques.

In what follows, “coupled” always refer to an electrical coupling. When applied to two items
25 such as terminals, conductors, nodes, etc, “coupled” may indicate that the items are directly
coupled, that is to say connected (or, equivalently, in electrical contact) to one another, and/or
that the items are indirectly coupled, in which case an electrical interaction different from direct
coupling exists between the items, for instance through one or more components. When applied
to two multi-terminal items, such as ports, connectors, etc, “coupled” may indicate that the items
30 are directly coupled, in which case each terminal of one of the items is directly coupled to one
and only one terminal of the other item, and/or that the items are indirectly coupled, in which
case an electrical interaction different from direct coupling exists between the terminals of the
items, for instance through one or more components. In what follows, “direct current” means
a current that is independent of time, and “d.c.” means direct current.

The apparatus of the invention is an antenna for radio transmission in a given frequency band, the antenna comprising:

- an unmanned aircraft, the unmanned aircraft comprising n “aircraft power input terminals” to receive electric power, where n is an integer greater than or equal to 2;
- 5 n electrical conductors, the n electrical conductors being insulated from one another, each of the n electrical conductors having a first end and a second end, the first end of said each of the n electrical conductors being coupled to one and only one of the n aircraft power input terminals, each of the n aircraft power input terminals being coupled to the first end of one and only one of the n electrical conductors;
- 10 a coupling network, the coupling network comprising n “coupling network power input terminals” to receive electric power outside the given frequency band, the coupling network comprising n paths for a direct current, each of said paths for a direct current existing from one and only one of the coupling network power input terminals to the second end of one and only one of the n electrical conductors, the coupling network
- 15 comprising a “signal terminal” for signals in the given frequency band, the coupling network comprising, for each of the n electrical conductors, a path for a current in the given frequency band, said path for a current in the given frequency band existing from the signal terminal to the second end of said each of the n electrical conductors.

For instance, each of said paths for a direct current may comprise an inductor, said inductor

20 having a first terminal and a second terminal, the first terminal of said inductor being directly or indirectly coupled to one of the coupling network power input terminals, the second terminal of said inductor being directly or indirectly coupled to the second end of one of the n electrical conductors. Said inductor may for instance be a choke coil. For instance, each of said paths for a direct current may present a d.c. resistance less than or equal to 10 ohms, and each of said

25 paths for a direct current may present, at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute value greater than or equal to 250 ohms.

For instance, each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band may comprise a capacitor, said capacitor having a terminal which is directly or indirectly coupled to the signal terminal. For instance, each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band may present,

30 at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute value less than or equal to 10 ohms, and each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band may present a d.c. resistance greater than or equal to 250 ohms.

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DRAWINGS

Other advantages and characteristics will appear more clearly from the following description

35 of particular embodiments of the invention, given by way of non-limiting examples, with reference to the accompanying drawings in which:

- Figure 1 is a drawing of an antenna of the invention (first and second embodiments);

- Figure 2 is a schematic diagram of an antenna of the invention (first embodiment);
- Figure 3 is a schematic diagram of an antenna of the invention (second embodiment);
- Figure 4 is a drawing of an implementation of an antenna of the invention (second embodiment);
- 5 - Figure 5 is a schematic diagram of an antenna of the invention (third embodiment).

DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF SOME EMBODIMENTS

First embodiment.

As a first embodiment of a device of the invention, given by way of non-limiting example, we have represented in Figure 1 a drawing of an antenna for radiocommunication in a given
10 frequency band, the given frequency band being a subset of the 500 kHz to 100 MHz frequency interval, the antenna comprising:

an unmanned aircraft (1), the unmanned aircraft comprising n “aircraft power input terminals” to receive electric power outside the given frequency band, where $n = 3$;
a cable (2) comprising n electrical conductors which are insulated from one another, each
15 of the n electrical conductors having a first end and a second end, the first end of said each of the n electrical conductors being coupled to one of the n aircraft power input terminals, each of the n aircraft power input terminals being coupled to the first end of one of the n electrical conductors;

a coupling network (3), the coupling network comprising n “coupling network power input terminals” to receive electric power, said electric power resulting from an applied
20 voltage at a frequency lower than any frequency in the given frequency band, the coupling network providing n paths for a direct current, each of said paths for a direct current existing between one and only one of the coupling network power input terminals and the second end of one and only one of the n electrical conductors, the
25 coupling network comprising a “signal terminal”, the signal terminal being intended to be used for signals in the given frequency band, the coupling network providing n paths for a current in the given frequency band, each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band existing between the signal terminal and the second end of one of the n electrical conductors.

30 Figure 2 shows a schematic diagram of the antenna. In Fig. 2, the cable (2) comprises a first electrical conductor (21), a second electrical conductor (22) and a third electrical conductor (23). The first electrical conductor (21) has a first end (211) and a second end (212). The second electrical conductor (22) has a first end (221) and a second end (222). The third electrical conductor (23) has a first end (231) and a second end (232). The first ends (211) (221) (231) of
35 the n electrical conductors are each coupled to one of the n aircraft power input terminals (141) (142) (143).

The coupling network (3) has a “coupling network power input connector” (31) comprising said n coupling network power input terminals (311) (312) (313). The coupling network comprises n inductors (331) (332) (333) used as choke coils, each of said inductors having a first terminal and a second terminal, the first terminal of said each of said inductors being directly
5 coupled to one and only one of the coupling network power input terminals, the second terminal of said each of said inductors being directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the n electrical conductors. The coupling network comprises n capacitors (351) (352) (353), each connected between one of the coupling network power input terminals and ground, these capacitors and said inductors forming n low-pass filters which each present, in the given
10 frequency band, a high impedance to the second end of one of the n electrical conductors. Said n paths for a direct current are: a first path from one of the coupling network power input terminals (311) to the second end (212) of the first electrical conductor, through one of the inductors (331); a second path from one of the coupling network power input terminals (312) to the second end (222) of the second electrical conductor, through one of the inductors (332);
15 and a third path from one of the coupling network power input terminals (313) to the second end (232) of the third electrical conductor, through one of the inductors (333). Each of said paths for a direct current presents a d.c. resistance less than or equal to 1 ohm, and each of said paths for a direct current presents, at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute value greater than or equal to 500 ohms.

20 It is also possible to say that the coupling network comprises, for each of the n coupling network power input terminals, a path for a direct current, said path for a direct current existing from said each of the n coupling network power input terminals to the second end of one and only one of the n electrical conductors. It is also possible to say that the coupling network comprises, for each of the n electrical conductors, a path for a direct current, said path for a
25 direct current existing from one and only one of the n coupling network power input terminals to the second end of said each of n electrical conductors.

The coupling network comprises n capacitors (341) (342) (343), each of these capacitors having a first terminal and a second terminal, the first terminal of said each of these capacitors being directly coupled to the signal terminal (321), the second terminal of said each of these
30 capacitors being directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the n electrical conductors. Said paths for a current in the given frequency band are: a first path from the signal terminal (321) to the second end (212) of the first electrical conductor, through one of said capacitors (341); a second path from the signal terminal (321) to the second end (222) of the second electrical conductor, through one of said capacitors (342); and a third path from the
35 signal terminal (321) to the second end (232) of the third electrical conductor, through one of said capacitors (343). Each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band presents, at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute value less than or equal to 1 ohm, and each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band presents an infinite d.c. resistance.

The unmanned aircraft (1) is capable of stationary flight. The unmanned aircraft comprises: said aircraft power input terminals (141) (142) (143); 3 capacitors (121) (122) (123); and all other electrical components of the unmanned aircraft (11). Said all other electrical components of the unmanned aircraft include one or more electric motors which provide the thrust necessary for flying. Under normal operation, the unmanned aircraft is intended to receive all the electric power it needs for flying from a generator coupled to the coupling network power input connector (31), said electric power being received through the inductors, the cable and the aircraft power input terminals. The electric power is provided by the generator in the form of a three-phase system at a frequency less than or equal to 1600 Hz. As regards the currents and voltages delivered by the generator, said electrical conductors are intended to substantially behave as 3 perfectly isolated electrical conductors.

Each of said paths for a direct current presenting a d.c. resistance less than or equal to 1 ohm and a nominal inductance less than or equal to 200 μ H, and each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band presenting an infinite d.c. resistance, the electric power received from the generator by the n coupling network power input terminals is efficiently (that is to say with zero or small loss) transferred to the second ends of the n electrical conductors. Thus, the electric power received from the generator coupled to the n coupling network power input terminals is efficiently used to provide power to the unmanned aircraft.

The unmanned aircraft is remote-controlled by utilizing a radio link, said radio link operating outside the given frequency band. For safety, the unmanned aircraft has an automatic landing function. One or more minimum voltages being defined, the automatic landing function is automatically triggered if: a voltage between two of said aircraft power input terminals (for instance, this voltage can be an rms voltage) is less than one of said one or more minimum voltages; and/or an electromagnetic interference is detected on the radio link utilized for remote-controlling the unmanned aircraft.

If the antenna is used for radio emission, a signal in the given frequency band is applied to the signal terminal (321), and excites currents flowing along said electrical conductors (21) (22) (23) and in the unmanned aircraft (1), said currents causing the radio emission. The unmanned aircraft must have a sufficiently high electromagnetic immunity to these currents. As regards these currents, said electrical conductors are intended to substantially behave as a single electrical conductor. To obtain this result, each of said capacitors (121) (122) (123) of the unmanned aircraft presents a low enough impedance at any frequency in the given frequency band, and each of said capacitors (341) (342) (343) having a first terminal directly coupled to the signal terminal presents a low enough impedance at any frequency in the given frequency band.

If the antenna is used for radio reception, incident electromagnetic waves in the given frequency band excite currents flowing along said electrical conductors (21) (22) (23) and in the unmanned aircraft (1), said currents causing a radio reception signal at the signal terminal (321). As regards these currents, said electrical conductors are intended to substantially behave as a

single electrical conductor. For a radio reception without interference caused by the unmanned aircraft, it must have a sufficiently low electromagnetic emission in the given frequency band.

We see that currents in the given frequency band, flowing along said electrical conductors (21) (22) (23) and in the unmanned aircraft (1), are excited when the antenna is used for radio emission and when the antenna is used for radio reception. This is the intended mode of operation of the antenna, in which the whole length of said electrical conductors substantially behaves as a single electrical conductor. This is entirely different from the intended mode of operation of the antenna structure disclosed in the United States Patent Application Publication number US 2017/0125893, entitled "Umbilical antenna structure", in which only a first section of a coaxial cable forms a radiating element, this radiating element being isolated from a second section of the coaxial cable.

Since each of said paths for a direct current presents, at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute value greater than or equal to 500 ohms, and since each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band presents, at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute value less than or equal to 1 ohm, signals in the given frequency band can be efficiently (that is to say with zero or small loss) transferred from the second ends of the n electrical conductors to the signal terminal (for radio reception), and from the signal terminal to the second ends of the n electrical conductors (for radio emission).

20 Second embodiment (best mode).

As a second embodiment of a device of the invention, given by way of non-limiting example and best mode of carrying out the invention, we have represented in Figure 1 a drawing of an antenna for radiocommunication in a given frequency band, the given frequency band being a subset of the 1 MHz to 30 MHz frequency interval, the antenna comprising:

- 25 an unmanned aircraft (1), the unmanned aircraft comprising n "aircraft power input terminals" to receive electric power, where $n = 2$;
- a cable (2) comprising n electrical conductors which are insulated from one another, each of the n electrical conductors having a first end and a second end, the first end of said each of the n electrical conductors being coupled to one and only one of the n aircraft power input terminals, each of the n aircraft power input terminals being coupled to the first end of one and only one of the n electrical conductors;
- 30 a coupling network (3), the coupling network comprising n "coupling network power input terminals" to receive electric power, said electric power resulting from a voltage that is substantially independent of time (direct voltage), the coupling network comprising 35 n paths for a direct current, each of said paths for a direct current existing from one and only one of the coupling network power input terminals to the second end of one and only one of the n electrical conductors, the coupling network comprising a "signal

terminal” to deliver and/or receive signals in the given frequency band, the coupling network comprising n paths for a current in the given frequency band, each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band existing from the signal terminal to the second end of one of the n electrical conductors.

5 Figure 3 shows a schematic diagram of the antenna. In Fig. 3, the cable (2) comprises a first electrical conductor (21) and a second electrical conductor (22). The first electrical conductor (21) has a first end (211) and a second end (212). The second electrical conductor (22) has a first end (221) and a second end (222). The first ends (211) (221) of the n electrical conductors are each coupled to one of the n aircraft power input terminals (141) (142).

10 The coupling network (3) has a “coupling network power input connector” (31) comprising said n coupling network power input terminals (311) (314). One of the coupling network power input terminals (314) is connected to the reference node (ground). The coupling network comprises n inductors (331) (334), each of said inductors having a first terminal and a second terminal, the first terminal of said each of said inductors being directly coupled to one and only
15 one of the coupling network power input terminals, the second terminal of said each of said inductors being directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the n electrical conductors. The coupling network comprises a capacitor (351) connected between one of the coupling network power input terminals and ground, this capacitor and one of the inductors (331) forming a low-pass filter which presents, in the given frequency band, a high impedance
20 to the second end (212) of one of the n electrical conductors. The other inductor (334) also presents a high impedance to the second end (222) of one of the n electrical conductors, in the given frequency band. Said n paths for a direct current are: a first path from one of the coupling network power input terminals (311) to the second end (212) of the first electrical conductor, through one of the inductors (331); and a second path from one of the coupling network power
25 input terminals (314) to the second end (222) of the second electrical conductor, through one of the inductors (334). Each of said paths for a direct current presents a d.c. resistance less than or equal to 0.02 ohm, and each of said paths for a direct current presents, at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute value greater than or equal to 1000 ohms.

30 The coupling network (3) has a “signal port” (32) comprising the signal terminal (321) and a terminal (322) connected to the reference node (ground). The coupling network also comprises: a capacitor (341) having a first terminal and a second terminal, the first terminal of this capacitor being directly coupled to the signal terminal (321), the second terminal of this capacitor being directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the n electrical
35 conductors (222); and a capacitor (344) having a first terminal and a second terminal, the first terminal of this capacitor being directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the n electrical conductors (212), the second terminal of this capacitor being directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the n electrical conductors (222). Said paths for a current in the given frequency band are: a first path from the signal terminal (321) to the second end (212)

of the first electrical conductor, through two of said capacitors (341) (344); and a second path from the signal terminal (321) to the second end (222) of the second electrical conductor, through one of said capacitors (341). Each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band presents, at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute value less than or equal to 0.2 ohm, and each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band presents a substantially infinite d.c. resistance.

The unmanned aircraft (1) is of the type commonly referred to as “drone” or “unmanned aerial vehicle”. More precisely, the unmanned aircraft is a quadcopter (that is to say a rotorcraft that is lifted by 4 rotors), weighing less than 3 kilograms. The unmanned aircraft comprises: said aircraft power input terminals (141) (142); a capacitor (124); and all other electrical components of the unmanned aircraft (11). Said all other electrical components of the unmanned aircraft include 4 electric motors which provide the thrust necessary for flying. Under normal operation, the unmanned aircraft is intended to receive all the electric power it needs for flying from a generator coupled to the coupling network power input connector (31), said electric power being received through the inductors, the cable and the aircraft power input terminals. The electric power is provided by the generator in the form of a voltage that is substantially independent of time. As regards the currents and voltages delivered by the generator, said electrical conductors are intended to behave like 2 perfectly isolated electrical conductors.

Since each of said paths for a direct current presents a d.c. resistance less than or equal to 0.02 ohm, and since each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band presents an infinite d.c. resistance, the electric power received from the generator by the n coupling network power input terminals is efficiently transferred to the second ends of the n electrical conductors. Thus, the electric power received from the generator coupled to the n coupling network power input terminals is efficiently used to provide power to the unmanned aircraft.

The unmanned aircraft is remote-controlled by utilizing a radio link, said radio link operating in the ISM band near 2.45 GHz, thus outside the given frequency band. For safety purpose, the unmanned aircraft has an automatic landing function which is automatically triggered if: the unmanned aircraft no longer receives, from (or through) the aircraft power input terminals, all the electric power it needs for flying; and/or electromagnetic interference is present on the radio link utilized for remote-controlling the unmanned aircraft. For instance, a minimum voltage being defined, the automatic landing function is automatically triggered if: a voltage between said aircraft power input terminals is less than said minimum voltage; and/or an electromagnetic interference is detected on the radio link utilized for remote-controlling the unmanned aircraft. For instance, an electromagnetic interference may be detected using an error detection code. The unmanned aircraft comprises a rechargeable battery, which can provide enough electric energy to safely perform the automatic landing function in the case where the unmanned aircraft does not receive, from (or through) the aircraft power input terminals, all the electric power it needs for flying. However, this rechargeable battery is small and light, because little energy is necessary to safely perform the automatic landing function.

If the antenna is used for radio emission, a signal in the given frequency band is applied to the signal port (32), and excites currents flowing along said electrical conductors (21) (22) and in the unmanned aircraft (1), said currents causing the radio emission. The unmanned aircraft must have a sufficiently high electromagnetic immunity to these currents. As regards these
5 currents, said electrical conductors are intended to behave like a single electrical conductor. To obtain this result, said capacitor (124) of the unmanned aircraft presents a low enough impedance at any frequency in the given frequency band, and said capacitor (344) having each of its terminals directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the n electrical
10 conductors presents a low enough impedance at any frequency in the given frequency band.

If the antenna is used for radio reception, incident electromagnetic waves in the given frequency band excite currents flowing along said electrical conductors (21) (22) and in the unmanned aircraft (1), said currents causing a radio reception signal at the signal port (32). As regards these currents, said electrical conductors are intended to behave like a single electrical
15 conductor. For a radio reception without interference caused by the unmanned aircraft, the unmanned aircraft must have a sufficiently low electromagnetic emission in the given frequency band.

We see that currents in the given frequency band, flowing along said electrical conductors (21) (22) and in the unmanned aircraft (1), are excited when the antenna is used for radio emission and when the antenna is used for radio reception.

Since each of said paths for a direct current presents, at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute value greater than or equal to 1000 ohms, and since each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band presents, at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute value less than or equal to 0.2 ohm, signals in the given frequency band can be efficiently (that is to say with zero or small loss)
20 transferred from the second ends of the n electrical conductors to the signal terminal (for radio reception), and from the signal terminal to the second ends of the n electrical conductors (for radio emission).

For radio emission and radio reception, the antenna is intended to operate almost as a vertical antenna, though the cable (2) is often not perfectly vertical. Figure 4 shows a drawing
30 of a use configuration of the antenna, the use configuration comprising:

- an unmanned aircraft (1) as explained above;
- a cable (2) as explained above;
- a coupling network (3) as explained above, the coupling network comprising said coupling network power input connector (31) and said signal port (32), the coupling network
35 laying on the soil surface (45);
- an earth connection (4) which couples the reference node (ground) of the coupling network to a ground system comprising 8 radial conductors (often referred to as “radials”) laid on the soil, and/or one or more ground rods driven into the soil;

- a transceiver (5) for radiocommunication in the given frequency band, this transceiver comprising an automatic antenna tuner;
- a coaxial cable (6) which couples the antenna port of the transceiver to the signal port (32);
- a power supply (7) which plays the role of the generator mentioned above;
- 5 a power supply cable (8) which couples the output of the power supply to the coupling network power input connector (31); and
- a remote control unit (9) which is used to control the unmanned aircraft.

The end of the cable (2) where the second ends of the n electrical conductors are connected to different nodes of the coupling network is attached to the envelope of the coupling network.

10 The other end of the cable (2) is attached to the unmanned aircraft. The unmanned aircraft has enough thrust to lift the cable (2), but not enough thrust to move the coupling network, so that the cable (2) takes on a nearly vertical position.

The remote control unit and the unmanned aircraft have an “automatic stationary flight” function, which, if manually activated, controls the flight to automatically obtain a nearly stationary and vertical position of the cable (2). This use configuration of the antenna can be

15 realized in less than 20 minutes by a single person, and it is not expensive. Thus, the antenna of the invention is a low-cost solution to the problem of realizing a reliable and efficient antenna for operation below 30 MHz, without the time and the space needed to erect a mast or a tower.

Third embodiment.

20 As a third embodiment of a device of the invention, given by way of non-limiting example, we have represented in Figure 5 a schematic diagram of an antenna for radiocommunication in a given frequency band. The given frequency band is the 3.5 MHz to 3.8 MHz frequency interval. The antenna comprises: an unmanned aircraft (1); a cable (2); and a coupling network (3). In Fig. 5, the cable (2) comprises a first electrical conductor (21) and a second electrical

25 conductor (22). The first electrical conductor (21) has a first end (211) and a second end (212). The second electrical conductor (22) has a first end (221) and a second end (222). The first ends (211) (221) of the 2 electrical conductors are each coupled to one of the 2 aircraft power input terminals (141) (142).

The coupling network (3) has a “coupling network power input connector” (31) comprising

30 2 coupling network power input terminals (311) (314). One of the coupling network power input terminals (314) is connected to the reference node (ground). The coupling network comprises 2 inductors (331) (334), each of said inductors having a first terminal and a second terminal, the first terminal of said each of said inductors being directly coupled to one and only one of the coupling network power input terminals, the second terminal of said each of said inductors being

35 directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the 2 electrical conductors. The coupling network comprises a capacitor (335) connected in parallel with one of the inductors (331) to obtain a first parallel resonant circuit presenting a very high impedance in the given

frequency band. The coupling network also comprises a capacitor (336) connected in parallel with the other inductor (334) to obtain a second parallel resonant circuit presenting a very high impedance in the given frequency band. Thus, the coupling network comprises: a first path for a direct current from one of the coupling network power input terminals (311) to the second end (212) of the first electrical conductor, through one of the inductors (331); and a second path for a direct current from one of the coupling network power input terminals (314) to the second end (222) of the second electrical conductor, through one of the inductors (334). Each of said paths for a direct current presents a d.c. resistance less than or equal to 0.02 ohm, and each of said paths for a direct current presents, at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute value greater than or equal to 5000 ohms.

The coupling network (3) has a "signal port" (32) comprising the signal terminal (321) and a terminal (322) connected to the reference node (ground). The coupling network also comprises: a capacitor (341) having a first terminal and a second terminal, the first terminal of this capacitor being directly coupled to the signal terminal (321), the second terminal of this capacitor being directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the 2 electrical conductors (222); a capacitor (342) having a first terminal and a second terminal, the first terminal of this capacitor being directly coupled to the signal terminal (321), the second terminal of this capacitor being directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the 2 electrical conductors (212); and a capacitor (344) having a first terminal and a second terminal, the first terminal of this capacitor being directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the 2 electrical conductors (212), the second terminal of this capacitor being directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the 2 electrical conductors (222). Thus, the coupling network comprises: a first path for a current in the given frequency band, from the signal terminal (321) to the second end (212) of the first electrical conductor, through one of said capacitors (342) in parallel with two of said capacitors (341) (344) connected in series; and a second path for a current in the given frequency band, from the signal terminal (321) to the second end (222) of the second electrical conductor, through one of said capacitors (341) in parallel with two of said capacitors (342) (344) connected in series. Each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band presents, at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute value less than or equal to 0.2 ohm, and each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band presents an infinite d.c. resistance.

The unmanned aircraft (1) comprises: said aircraft power input terminals (141) (142); a capacitor (124); two inductors (131) (132); and all other electrical components of the unmanned aircraft (11).

The specialist understands that, to use the antenna for radio emission and radio reception in the given frequency band, it is necessary that: said electrical conductors (21) (22) substantially behave as a single electrical conductor for a current flowing along said conductors, at any frequency in the given frequency band; the unmanned aircraft has a sufficiently high

electromagnetic immunity to currents flowing along said conductors and excited by a signal applied to the signal port in the given frequency band; and the unmanned aircraft has a sufficiently low electromagnetic emission in the given frequency band. Said capacitor (124) and said two inductors (131) (132) of the unmanned aircraft form a low-pass filter presenting a low impedance to the cable (2) at any frequency in the given frequency band, which contributes to satisfy these requirements. Said capacitors (341) (342) each having a first terminal which is directly coupled to the signal terminal (321) and a second terminal which is directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the 2 electrical conductors, and said capacitor (344) having a first terminal which is directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the 2 electrical conductors (212) and a second terminal which is directly coupled to the second end of one and only one of the 2 electrical conductors (222), present a low impedance at any frequency in the given frequency band, so that they also contribute to satisfy said requirements.

In a use configuration of the antenna, the coupling network may be attached to a land vehicle, and used when the land vehicle does not move.

15 INDICATIONS ON INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

The antenna of the invention can be rapidly deployed in the field. It is suitable for reliable and efficient radiocommunication, without the time, the cost and the space needed to erect a mast or a tower.

The antenna of the invention is particularly suitable to quickly create a high performance station for radio emission and/or radio reception in the medium frequency band (hectometric waves) and/or in the high frequency band (decametric waves). The antenna of the invention is suitable for long-range emergency radiocommunications in the context of a disaster, and for long-range tactical radiocommunications, in particular in circumstances where radiocommunications by satellite cannot be used. The antenna of the invention is also suitable for the amateur service, in particular for expeditions.

CLAIMS

1. An antenna for radiocommunication in a given frequency band, the antenna comprising:
an unmanned aircraft (1), the unmanned aircraft comprising n “aircraft power input
terminals” (141) (142) (143) to receive electric power, where n is an integer greater
5 than or equal to 2;
 n electrical conductors (21) (22) (23), the n electrical conductors being insulated from one
another, each of the n electrical conductors having a first end and a second end, the
first end of said each of the n electrical conductors being coupled to one and only one
of the n aircraft power input terminals, each of the n aircraft power input terminals
10 being coupled to the first end of one and only one of the n electrical conductors;
a coupling network (3), the coupling network comprising n “coupling network power input
terminals” to receive electric power outside the given frequency band, the coupling
network comprising n paths for a direct current, each of said paths for a direct current
existing from one and only one of the coupling network power input terminals to the
15 second end of one and only one of the n electrical conductors, the coupling network
comprising a “signal terminal” for signals in the given frequency band, the coupling
network comprising, for each of the n electrical conductors, a path for a current in the
given frequency band, said path for a current in the given frequency band existing
from the signal terminal to the second end of said each of the n electrical conductors.
20
2. The antenna of claim 1, wherein a cable (2) comprises said n electrical conductors.
3. The antenna of any one of the previous claims, wherein each of said paths for a direct
current comprises an inductor, said inductor having a first terminal and a second terminal, the
first terminal of said inductor being directly or indirectly coupled to one of the coupling network
power input terminals, the second terminal of said inductor being directly or indirectly coupled
25 to the second end of one of the n electrical conductors.
4. The antenna of any one of the previous claims, wherein each of said paths for a direct
current presents a d.c. resistance less than or equal to 10 ohms.
5. The antenna of any one of the previous claims, wherein each of said paths for a direct
current presents, at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute
30 value greater than or equal to 250 ohms.
6. The antenna of any one of the previous claims, wherein each of said paths for a current in
the given frequency band comprises a capacitor, said capacitor having a terminal which is
directly or indirectly coupled to the signal terminal.

7. The antenna of any one of the previous claims, wherein each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band presents, at any frequency in the given frequency band, an impedance having an absolute value less than or equal to 10 ohms.
8. The antenna of any one of the previous claims, wherein each of said paths for a current in
5 the given frequency band presents a d.c. resistance greater than or equal to 250 ohms.
9. The antenna of any one of the previous claims, wherein each of said paths for a current in the given frequency band presents a substantially infinite d.c. resistance.
10. The antenna of any one of the previous claims, wherein the unmanned aircraft is remote-controlled.
- 10 11. The antenna of any one of the claims 1 to 9, wherein the unmanned aircraft is remote-controlled by utilizing a radio link, said radio link operating outside the given frequency band.
12. The antenna of any one of the previous claims, wherein the unmanned aircraft has an automatic landing function.
13. The antenna of claim 12, wherein, one or more minimum voltages being defined, said
15 automatic landing function is automatically triggered if a voltage between two of said aircraft power input terminals is less than one of said one or more minimum voltages.
14. The antenna of the claims 11 and 12, wherein said automatic landing function is automatically triggered if an electromagnetic interference is detected on the radio link.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

INTERNATIONAL SEARCH REPORT

International application No
PCT/IB2017/057346

A. CLASSIFICATION OF SUBJECT MATTER
INV. H01Q1/28 H01Q1/46 B64C39/00
ADD.
According to International Patent Classification (IPC) or to both national classification and IPC

B. FIELDS SEARCHED
Minimum documentation searched (classification system followed by classification symbols)
H01Q B64C

Documentation searched other than minimum documentation to the extent that such documents are included in the fields searched

Electronic data base consulted during the international search (name of data base and, where practicable, search terms used)
EPO-Internal, WPI Data

C. DOCUMENTS CONSIDERED TO BE RELEVANT

Category*	Citation of document, with indication, where appropriate, of the relevant passages	Relevant to claim No.
A	FR 2 707 386 A1 (THOMSON CSF [FR]) 13 January 1995 (1995-01-13) page 8, line 11 - line 25; figure 9 -----	1-14
A	US 2014/327733 A1 (WAGREICH DAVID [US]) 6 November 2014 (2014-11-06) paragraph [0087] - paragraph [0095]; figures 1,2 -----	1
A	GB 481 950 A (STANDARD TELEPHONES CABLES LTD; CHARLES FREDERICK ALLEN WAGSTA) 18 March 1938 (1938-03-18) page 1, column 2, line 84 - page 2, column 1, line 2; figure 2 -----	1
A	US 2015/184639 A1 (GOESSLING ANDREW [US] ET AL) 2 July 2015 (2015-07-02) paragraph [0067] - paragraph [0081]; figure 3A -----	1

Further documents are listed in the continuation of Box C.

See patent family annex.

* Special categories of cited documents :

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Date of the actual completion of the international search

14 February 2018

Date of mailing of the international search report

23/02/2018

Name and mailing address of the ISA/

European Patent Office, P.B. 5818 Patentlaan 2
NL - 2280 HV Rijswijk
Tel. (+31-70) 340-2040,
Fax: (+31-70) 340-3016

Authorized officer

Degraeve, Alexis

INTERNATIONAL SEARCH REPORT

Information on patent family members

International application No PCT/IB2017/057346

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